

**Role of Panchayati Raj Institutions in Promoting
Child Care Services: A Study of Lucknow &
Bahraich Districts of Uttar Pradesh**

Thesis

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Jamia Millia Islamia

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Degree of Doctor of Philosophy
Early Child Development

By

Md. Shahadat Hussain

Under the Supervision of

Prof. Zubair Meenai
Centre for Early Childhood
Development & Research

Prof. Ashvini Kumar Singh
Department of Social Work
Jamia Millia Islamia, New Delhi

Centre for Early Childhood Development and Research,
Jamia Millia Islamia, New Delhi – 110025

October, 2022

Declaration

I **Md. Shahadat Hussain**, student of Ph.D. hereby declare that the thesis titled, **“ROLE OF PANCHYATI RAJ INSTITUTIONS IN PROMOTING CHILD CARE SERVICES: A STUDY OF LUCKNOW & BAHRAICH DISTRICTS OF UTTAR PRADESH”** which is submitted by me to the Centre for Early Childhood Development and Research, Jamia Millia Islamia, New Delhi, in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the award of the degree of the Doctor of Philosophy has not been previously formed the basis for the award of any Degree, Diploma, Associateship, Fellowship or other similar title or recognition. This is to declare further that I have also fulfilled the requirements of Para 11 ((a) to 11 (1)) of the Ph. D. Ordinance, the details of which are enclosed at the end of the Dissertation/Thesis, and that there is no plagiarism.

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Md. Shahadat Hussain

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Place & Date: New Delhi

Prof. Zubair Meenai

(Supervisor)
Centre for Early Childhood
Development & Research

Prof. Ashvini Kumar Singh

(Co-Supervisor)
Department of Social Work

Dr. Archana Dassi 31/10/2022
Professor Incharge

Centre for Early Childhood Development and Research,
Jamia Millia Islamia, New Delhi – 110025

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